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Investigation of Compression Strength Enhancement in 3D-Printed Hollow Structures Using Granular Backfill

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Abstract. The recent state of technology shows that the advantages of Direct Polymer Additive Tooling (DPAT) in sheet metal forming operations, e.g. low production cost and time, lose significance with increasing size of the formed part since it is strongly dependent on the limited flow of material on a 3D printer.

This study presents the results of a feasibility study regarding the potential of material reduction in DPAT. For that, a preliminary parameter study for the specimen geometry was carried out. Based on the findings, the four most promising parameter sets were selected for compression tests.

The results demonstrate the efficacy of compressed granular material in back-filling structures with low filling density, thereby enhancing the load-bearing capacity of hollow printed parts.

It is shown that the presented material reduction strategy has the potential to bring back the advantages of DPAT for components with larger dimensions. In accordance with the principles of circular economy and sustainable production, the approach focuses exclusively on the use of biodegradable polymer materials combined with natural and reusable backfill materials.

Keywords: Additive Tooling, Rapid Prototyping, Material Reduction, Sheet Metal Forming

1 Introduction

The utilization of additively manufactured deep drawing tools provides significant benefits in creating prototypes, thanks to their reduced manufacturing times and costs. According to the current state of technology, Direct Polymer Additive Tooling (DPAT) can be used on a small scale with high dimensional accuracy. However, an increase in component size reaches its limits due to material consumption and production time. In order to increase the component size, a strategy to reduce the amount of material extruded is needed. When coupled with flexible manufacturing processes, this technology can enable economical production of deep-drawn components, even for low-volume orders.

The first chapter of this study describes the motivation and state of research in the field of material reduction for DPAT. The second chapter deals with the methodology

used for substitution of backfill material. The third and fourth chapters present and discuss the results of the conducted experiments. The work is completed with a conclusion on the potential for further investigations on that topic.

1.1 Motivation

The automotive industry is under increasing pressure to respond flexibly to the dynamic market and to constantly changing technological requirements. The increasing demand for a large variety of products due to region-specific regulations and upcoming mass personalization represents an additional challenge for the short production cycle of required forming tools. The production of prototypes and rare or discontinued car body parts is an additional promising field of future application for polymer additive tooling. As **Fig. 1** shows, the number of owned classic cars in Germany has tripled within the last 10 years. From that, a rising demand for single or small batch production of (spare) parts in general can be expected in the next years.

Fig. 1. Number of Owned Classic Cars (in thousand) between 2014 and 2024 in Germany (Data from [1, 2])

Established manufacturing processes, such as deep drawing with precision milled tools made of steel, require investments in tooling. During single piece, prototype or small series production this results in very high unit costs. For this reason, research is conducted around polymer-additive forming tools as a cost-effective alternative. Initial research results show that additively manufactured embossing and deep-drawing tools out of polylactic acid (PLA) are capable of producing sheet metal components in small batches and the dimensional deviation is within an acceptable range for prototyping purposes. [3, 4]

To break through the correlation between time, cost and material consumption in additive manufacturing because of the limited extrusion rate of a 3D printer, this study presents an approach on reducing extruded material while the compression strength of the parts is enhanced through filling material. This could also enable DPAT to be used in other areas of application (e.g. thermoforming).

1.2 State of Research

Large-Scale Additive Manufacturing. Cost-efficient manufacturing methods such as polymer milling or resin casting are commonly known and employed for the production of forming tools [5, 6]. However, these approaches involve multiple processing steps and manual intervention, increasing both lead time and expenses. Direct polymer additive tooling provides an alternative by utilizing polymer-based additive manufacturing (AM) techniques to produce forming tools without relying on indirect methods like casting. While DPAT has been widely explored for injection molding applications [7, 8], its potential for deep-drawing tool fabrication remains largely unexplored. Most research in sheet metal forming with DPAT focuses on bending or embossing rather than deep drawing. [9–11]

The performance of printed parts is influenced by multiple parameters, including material selection, layer orientation relative to applied forces, the chosen infill pattern and infill ratio. [12, 13] For large-scale printed forming tools, material consumption significantly affects both production time and cost as the application requires a high infill ratio in order to achieve maximum compression strength.

To improve manufacturing efficiency of DPAT, it is a promising approach to create a hollow shell design with an optimized infill structure. In this case, the reduced performance of the part must be compensated by using a suitable filling material within the internal cavities. This approach has yet not been investigated.

Backfill Materials. Potential fillers include epoxy resins and concrete, yet a critical assessment from a circular economy perspective reveals their limitations. Epoxy resins, despite their high mechanical performance and versatility, raise concerns due to their toxicity and environmental impact. [14] The release of bisphenol A (BPA) during production and processing presents health hazards [15], while their thermosetting nature complicates recycling. Unlike thermoplastics, which can be remelted and reintegrated into production cycles, thermosets cannot be efficiently reprocessed, often resulting in downcycling into lower-value materials. [16] Concrete, although exhibiting lower toxicity, introduces additional risks such as silicosis, a lung disease caused by inhalation of crystalline silica particles. This hazard becomes particularly relevant during post-processing, including mechanical separation of cured concrete from tooling components. [17] Moreover, the high CO₂ emissions associated with cement production significantly impact sustainability. Recycling possibilities for concrete remain limited, as its secondary use is generally restricted to low-grade aggregates [18].

Given these constraints, the selection of filler materials should prioritize non-toxicity and full recyclability to ensure sustainability. Suitable alternatives include quartz sand and other granular substances that do not require curing. These materials have not been investigated so far for additive tooling.

Geosynthetic-Encased Sand Columns. In geotechnical and civil engineering applications, granular material is extensively used in geosynthetic-encased sand columns (GESCs). Geosynthetics, typically polymer-based composites or nonwoven fabrics, are employed to transfer horizontal loads into load-bearing layers, enhancing structural integrity. In non-encased columns, horizontal stress resulting from axial loading must be counterbalanced by an equivalent force within the surrounding soft material. Encased

columns, however, benefit from the supporting effect of the geosynthetic enclosure. As the diameter expands beyond the initial installation width, induced strain generates a counteracting stress within the encasement. [19]

The resulting hoop tensile forces are governed by the elastic modulus of the geosynthetic material and adhere to Hooke's law, aligning with the column's horizontal deformation. In the context of toolmaking, where no surrounding soft layer is present, the encasement must independently counteract stresses to maintain overall stability. [19]

The occurring stresses and the structure of such a column is shown in Fig. 2. As a result, the sand column gains enhanced load-bearing capacity and is capable of withstanding substantially higher compressive loads.

Fig. 2. Technical Representation of Geosynthetic-Encased Sand Columns (modified from [19])

Assuming a homogeneous composition, quartz sand can be simplified as granular material, which consists of individual particles governed by the principles of classical mechanics. In dry granular material, cohesion is negligible, meaning that force transmission occurs exclusively through friction, classifying these systems as dissipative [20]. Under specific conditions, sand can exhibit different states of aggregation. For

example, it behaves in a fluid-like manner when subjected to vibrations, a phenomenon that facilitates the attainment of maximum packing density [21].

The optimal packing density is determined by the coordination number, which quantifies the number of direct neighboring contacts within a given plane.

The physical property of dilatancy describes the tendency of granular material to expand in volume under shear stress. This effect, first documented in 1885 by OSBORNE REYNOLDS, is commonly observed in materials such as sand, emulsions, and foams. It is closely linked to the response of granular systems to shear and normal stresses, as well as their internal structure. **Fig. 3** illustrates granular material with high density (top row) and low density (bottom row). During shear deformation, highly compacted granular packings experience volumetric expansion due to particle rearrangement and the formation of additional contact points. In a closed system like a sand column, this leads to an increase in stiffness, thereby enhancing the overall stability. For granular material with low density, the rearrangement causes a volumetric contraction as the density increases . [22, 20, 23]

Fig. 3. Packing Density of Granular Material [20]

1.3 Research Deficit and Research Question

Polymer additive manufacturing of forming tools is actually a promising production method for sheet metal parts since various examinations showed the practicability and the potentials regarding time and cost savings in forming tool production [24, 25].

First published research results show, that the deviation of formed parts can be reduced by stiffening (increasing compression strength) the forming tools made out of polymer material with additional material layers or metal inserts [26, 11]. The wear (predominantly plastic deformation) of the forming tools is interdependent with the amount of extruded polymeric material.

Furthermore, tooling cost as well as the lead time can be significantly reduced by the direct additive manufacturing of deep-drawing tools [27]. However, it must not be ignored that the volume increases cubically with the side length of a plastic body, whereby the advantage in production time and cost is revised with increasing volume or equivalent the amount of material to be extruded by a 3D printer. That makes DPAT questionable for the application on components with bigger dimensions, since it has not

been investigated yet [27]. Besides that, the main disadvantages of this technology up to this point is the low hardness of the polymer (plastic and elastic deformation) used and the linear dependency between tool volume, production time and cost.

This results in the research question, which is the basis for the present study to make the technology of additively manufactured sheet metal forming tools universally applicable on different geometries with consistent forming quality in the future: “How must an additively manufactured polymer forming tool be designed to achieve maximum compression stiffness while minimizing the amount of extruded material?”

2 Methodology

The following section outlines the methodology applied in this research. It begins with the definition of the specimen design, followed by the results of a simulation-based preliminary parameter study. Subsequently, the findings of the experimental investigations on the compressive strength of the 3D-printed specimens are presented.

2.1 Definition of the Specimen

The standardized specimen specified in EN ISO 604:2003, which is commonly used for polymeric materials, is not suitable for evaluating filled polymers, as its prescribed diameter of 4 mm is insufficient to properly capture the interaction between the granular material and the surrounding polymer matrix [28]. In this case, dilatancy effects do not manifest significantly, particularly when using granular substances that are safe to handle.

Fig. 4. Reference Geometry and Investigated Parameters

To address this limitation, a cylindrical specimen with a diameter of 25 mm, a height of 25 mm, and a wall thickness of 1 mm was derived, based on the guidelines for metallic materials provided in DIN 50106:2023-02. [29] **Fig. 4** shows the selected reference geometry in the center, hereinafter referred to as [0].

2.2 Parameter Study

For this geometry, a parameter study was conducted to assess the influence of the selected design parameters on the compression strength of the specimen. To achieve this, a two-step simulation approach was employed: initially, a Finite Element Method (FEM) model was used to analyze the shell geometry, followed by a Discrete Element Method (DEM) model to simulate the behavior of the granular filler material under compression force.

Five key parameters were varied: wall thickness (1 mm [0], 2.5 mm [A]), bracing configuration (none [0], straight [B], and centrally kinked), inner and outer wall structuring (openings [C], ribbed [D]), conicity of the outer wall (straight, narrowing, widening), and granular filling. In total, 32 simulation runs were performed.

The configurations A, B, ABC, and ABD shown in **Fig. 5** reached the highest compressive strength among all simulated parameter combinations. Configuration P (100% infill) served as the reference specimen for validating the results through physical compression testing.

Fig. 5. Configurations with Highest Compression Strength

2.3 Experiments

For the conducted experiments, a sample size of four specimens per geometry was selected to ensure sufficient statistical relevance. The specimens were fabricated using Ultimaker PLA filament with an Ultimaker S5 3D printer. The corresponding printing parameters are listed in **Table 1**.

Two of the four specimens were subsequently filled with quartz sand (grain size 0.1 mm to 0.5 mm) and compacted under the influence of vibration. During this process, the mass was recorded both before and after filling to evaluate the repeatability of the procedure. **Table 2** provides an overview of the measured values, which were determined using a precision scale with a resolution of 0.01 g. The data indicates a filling accuracy of 0.3 g with the applied setup and a mass variation of the unfilled 3D-printed

PLA specimens of up to 0.18 g. The unfilled specimens serve as a reference, indicating the effect of the filling on the compression strength of the parts. The experiments were conducted under uncontrolled climate conditions.

Table 1. 3D Printing Parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Nozzle Diameter	0.4 mm	Infill Pattern	Triangles
Layer Height	0.2 mm	Infill Density	73%
Number of Wall Lines	6	Printing Speed	80 mm/s
Number of Bottom Lines	5	Build Plate Adhesion	Brim

Table 2. Mass of the Specimens

Specimen	Mass [g]			Specimen	Mass [g]		
	Unfilled	Filled	Filling		Unfilled	Filled	Filling
A1	4.90	16.33	11.43	ABC1	6.75	15.76	9.01
A2	4.84	16.18	11.34	ABC2	6.66	15.53	8.87
A3	4.85	-	-	ABC3	6.58	-	-
A4	4.86	-	-	ABC4	6.57	-	-
B1	3.39	18.2	14.81	ABD1	6.79	14.77	7.98
B2	3.41	17.92	14.51	ABD2	6.81	14.58	7.77
B3	3.39	-	-	ABD3	6.88	-	-
B4	3.43	-	-	ABD4	6.79	-	-
P1	8.02	-	-	P3	8.07	-	-
P2	8.07	-	-	P4	8.14	-	-

During the experiments, specimens are centered on the lower plate of the *ZwickRoell AllroundLine Z250 SN* testing machine, as shown in **Fig. 6**. The compression plates are initially set to a distance of 27 mm, and testing is performed at a constant speed of 2 mm/min, terminating at a plate distance of 22.5 mm. The system is then returned to the starting position.

Fig. 6. Experimental Setup

3 Analysis and Results

This section presents the experimental results of the force-displacement behavior of the filled and unfilled specimen configurations. For better clarity, two similar configurations are always compared with each other. In the end, all four configurations are compared to the reference specimen with 100% infill.

The following **Fig. 7** shows the results for configurations A and B. Specimen A has a 2.5 mm wall thickness in comparison to the reference geometry. The filled specimens A1 and A2 reach maximum forces of 10294 N and 9942 N at displacements of 2.81 mm and 2.93 mm, respectively. In contrast, the unfilled specimens A3 and A4 peak at 4530 N and 4230 N at 1.16 mm and 1.5 mm. The experimental results demonstrate that filled specimens exhibit a force-displacement response similar to that of the unfilled specimens up to a compression of 1 mm. Beyond this point, the compressive force in the filled specimens increases continuously, reaching a peak at approximately 2.8 mm, followed by a plateau, which indicates the onset of structural stabilization. In contrast, the unfilled specimens show signs of failure initiation around 1 mm compression, likely due to the progressive collapse of internal layers. This collapse leads to a redistribution of the applied load, resulting in a force plateau in the range of 1 mm to 2.5 mm, reflecting the system's limited ability to further resist deformation.

Fig. 7. Results of Specimens A and B

In Specimen B, the integration of internal support elements alters the mechanical response compared to the reference geometry. The filled variants reach peak forces of 8303 N (B1) and 7972 N (B2) at displacements of 1.79 mm and 1.90 mm, respectively. In contrast, the unfilled specimens peak at 4600 N (B3) and 4740 N (B4) at 1.11 mm and 1.13 mm. Following the peak load, the unfilled specimens fail abruptly without forming a force plateau, likely due to their reduced wall thickness and limited structural redundancy. Up to the maximum force of the unfilled variants, configurations A and B exhibit a comparable force-displacement response. Additionally, Specimen B1 outperforms B2, which can be attributed to a slightly lower filling mass in B2 (0.3 g less). The following **Fig. 8** shows the difference between an unfilled and a filled specimen for the configurations A and B after the compression tests were carried out. In the upper

region, the specimens' walls collapse, forming a wave-like deformation. In the lower region, the specimens exhibit significant radial expansion. The influence of the sand filling on wall stability is clearly visible, with Specimens A and B showing the most pronounced differences. In the unfilled state, their walls deform more strongly and asymmetrically compared to the filled counterparts.

A polygonal cross-section is observed in the top view of the unfilled specimens, whereas this feature is absent in the filled counterparts. This phenomenon is attributed to the suppression of wall buckling, particularly around the openings, when granular filling is present. In contrast, the unfilled specimens show visible dents and notches, which indicate the local collapse of individual structural layers due to insufficient internal support.

Fig. 8. Specimens A and B after Experiments

The following **Fig. 9** shows the force-displacement curves for the configurations ABC and ABD. Specimen ABC combines 2.5 mm wall thickness, internal supports, and wall structuring with openings. The filled variants reach maximum forces of 12417 N (ABC1) and 12,235 N (ABC2) at 3.00 mm, while the unfilled counterparts peak at 6503 N (ABC3) and 6318 N (ABC4) at 2.58 mm and 3.00 mm, respectively.

Fig. 9. Results of Specimens ABC and ABD

Specimen ABD, featuring ribbed walls instead of openings, reaches 10230 N (ABD1) and 10,137 N (ABD2) at 3.00 mm when filled, whereas the unfilled specimens peak at 4977 N (ABD3) and 4579 N (ABD4) at 2.32 mm and 1.35 mm.

In summary, the filled specimens exhibit no distinct peak, while the unfilled specimens display behavior similar to configuration A, with a force plateau following the maximum.

Fig. 10 shows the deformed geometries. Compared to configurations A and B, ABC and ABD exhibit less pronounced deformation. In ABC, layer separation occurs near the outer diameter, forming a visible bulge. In ABD, lower layers delaminate, and over-stressing of internal layers leads to the formation of loose filament strands within the structure.

Fig. 10. Specimens ABC and ABD after experiments

Fig. 11 presents the force-displacement curves for specimens A1, B1, ABC1, ABD1, and P1. It is evident that specimens incorporating internal support structures (parameter B) exhibit a more gradual increase in force within the elastic deformation range, while specimens A1 and P1 demonstrate a steeper initial slope.

Fig. 11. Comparison of Configurations A, B, ABC, ABD and P

The early portion of the curve appears to be less affected by the presence of granular filling compared to the later stages of the experiment. The initial stiffness (slope of the curve) of A1 and P1 is comparable. Nevertheless, despite their lower initial stiffness, specimens B1, ABC1, and ABD1 attain higher peak compressive forces than the reference specimen P1, indicating improved load-bearing capacity due to their internal design features.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

The experimental results demonstrate high repeatability, particularly in the elastic region, where force-displacement curves across repeated trials are nearly identical. Deviations become more apparent in the plastic region, where the degree of sand compaction significantly influences mechanical performance. Solid specimens show minimal variance. Based on the combined findings, the following design recommendations can be derived for additively manufactured forming tools:

Wall Thickness. A minimum of 2 mm is recommended for outer walls under axial loading to initiate effective dilatancy effects. That ensures direct load transmission to the base plate, avoiding shell-only designs. To reduce stress concentrations and radial displacement limitations, FEM-based design support is advised.

Support Strategies. For complex geometries, internal reinforcements should be placed beneath critical contours, as they deform independently under load. A promising approach is a cylindrical infill pattern with columns (3–5 mm diameter, 1 mm wall thickness) distributed across the base, shown in the following **Fig. 12**, offering efficient reinforcement with high design flexibility. The color gradient in the figures represent a Finite Element Method (FEM) simulation, which shows that during compression, central voids between support columns collapse, resulting in localized compaction of the granular filler. This compaction enhances the load-bearing capacity of the structure. Due to the narrow spacing between adjacent columns, material flow is restricted, effectively isolating the central filling from the outer regions. The described infill strategy can be readily implemented in CAD software using pattern-based design tools.

Fig. 12. Specimen with Uniformly Distributed Support Columns

For rotationally symmetric components, concentric column arrangements are a feasible option, as illustrated in **Fig. 13**. In cases involving small diameters, the use of a single, narrow support structure is also effective, ensuring compliance with surface deformation constraints while improving force transmission through the granular material.

Fig. 13. Specimen with Concentric Support Columns

This study demonstrates that the use of hollow columns as internal supports and wall thicknesses exceeding 2 mm proved particularly beneficial for the application case of this study. Based on these findings, a set of design guidelines for additively manufactured, granular-filled hollow structures were derived under consideration of the limited physical properties of PLA material. It is recommended to partition the internal volume using either multiple distributed columns or coaxial column structures, depending on the application and geometric constraints.

Furthermore, quartz sand is a suitable granular filler for reinforcing cylindrical specimens made from PLA material. The results indicate that maintaining equivalent maximum load capacity is possible while reducing the outer shell material by over 55%. Based on that, with only a moderate higher 3D printed material rate, the maximum compressive force can be increased by up to 50% while the reusability of the granular filler and the reduction in production time contribute to improved sustainability and manufacturing efficiency.

5 Outlook

To further advance this research, several promising directions have been identified. A key area is the integration of direct FEM-DEM coupling, which would allow for a more realistic representation of the interaction between granular filler materials and the surrounding shell structures.

Another critical aspect is the reduction of the compression path required by the granular filler. Strategies such as pre-compaction, prestressing of the shell, or the use of alternative outer materials should be investigated to improve the structural efficiency of the system and minimize deformation under load.

The methodology and findings presented in this study can also be extended to forming technologies, including embossing, thermoforming and hydroforming, where the interaction between flexible shell structures and internal fillers plays a central role in shaping performance outcomes.

Further optimization may be achieved by modifying internal geometries to improve the load-bearing behavior of the filler. Adjustments to rib patterns, column placement, or other support structures offer the potential to tailor both stiffness and energy absorption characteristics to specific application requirements.

Finally, a more detailed investigation of the particle size distribution and material type of the granular filler is expected to yield valuable insights. Understanding how these parameters influence dilatancy, compaction behavior, and structural reinforcement could further improve the applicability and performance of granular filled, additively manufactured forming tools.

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